

STUDY IMPROVEMENT OF THE UNIFIED MEDICAL INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL SYSTEM FOR THE MATERIALS

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Relevance. In the modern process of globalization, various means of communication (ICT), including computers and the Internet, are widely used in all sectors of the economy. In turn, one of the most pressing issues is the creation of specific equipment for each service sector, production, science and special software systems that ensure the operation of this equipment. To date, our country has also achieved certain results in improving the results of optimizing the network of medical institutions, the formation of a modern system of medical care. Also, as a result of the activities carried out, the most relevant of them were identified.

Purpose of the study. In-depth study and analysis of the activities of the medical contingent of periodic medical examinations, improvement of a unified medical information and analytical system using information and communication technologies and the creation of a special program.

Research methods. The contingent for medical examination in the Kibray district of the Tashkent region. The main object is the staff of the district system of public education (2000), the staff of district medical institutions. Quantitative and qualitative indicators of periodic medical examinations of the population of the Kibray district of the Tashkent region in district medical institutions, health care of the district, district medical association, health status of employees of medical institutions, morbidity, treatment, medical examinations and dynamics of medical care; state of medical records of contract contingents; the state of the electronic information system and information exchange in the district medical association.

Results and discussions of the study. The study includes an analysis of the current state of the organization of medical examination of the population, the development of organizational and methodological measures to improve the system of medical examination of the population, and an assessment of effectiveness. It also describes the problems and ways of introducing interdepartmental integration systems for medical examination of the population based on computer technology. Kibray district of Tashkent region is determined by its specificity, location, population and density, uniquely

developed infrastructure, concentration of industry and other enterprises located in the central socio-economic zone of the region.

Conclusions. The number of enterprises and employees of the Kibray region, which are required to undergo a mandatory medical examination, has been specified and their electronic register has been compiled for the region. Insufficient implementation of information and communication technologies in the healthcare system, excessive document flow, excessive bureaucratization and high cost are factors affecting the completeness and accuracy of the medical examination of the contingent. Mandatory medical examinations have refined the scope and quality of medical examinations, as well as their accuracy. The program developed so far includes 1010 descriptive cohorts and evaluates the reliability of medical examinations conducted between them. An electronic analytical database has been created using ICT. An interdepartmental automated program for monitoring medical examinations of the maternal contingent has been developed and is being implemented. Ministry of Justice The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Agency for Intellectual Property issued certificates under the EKS program for medical examination of the contingent and the DC program for the medical examination of the contingent.

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